

Special issue

Article

DNA nanomachine to target miR-21 and determine its structural and functional characteristics

Sajad Shariat 1, S. Javad Mowla 2, Ali Jebali 1

1 Department of Nanotechnology, TMS.C., Islamic Azad University, Tehran, Iran. 2 Genetics Department, Faculty of Biological Sciences, Tarbiat Modares University, Tehran, Iran. Corresponding author: Ali Jebali, Department of Medical Nanotechnology, Faculty of Advanced Sciences and Technology, Tehran Medical Science, Islamic Azad University, Tehran, Iran. Email: alijebal2011@gmail.com

Abstract:

The purpose of this study was to design a new DNA nanomachine without the use of nanoparticles and a large number of sequences, as well as a much lower design and center cost. In this study, a DNA nanomachine based on single-stranded oligonucleotides was designed and synthesized to target miR-21. The method of synthesis was such that after the synthesis of the designed oligonucleotides, the concentration of 20 nM of them was first prepared and after dilution, they were all adjusted to 1 nM. Then 10 microliters of each was taken separately and poured into a microtube and incubated at 95 for 5 minutes. Then the reaction mixture reached the ambient temperature in the form of a gradient for 15 minutes. This solution was used for structural and functional characterization which included DLS (dynamic light scattering) and AFM (Atomic force microscopy) methods and horizontal electrophoresis with 2% agarose and melting curve with real-time PCR method. DLS test in this study showed a reduction in the size of DNA nanomachine nanoparticles with the intervention of miR-21. The size range of DNA nanomachine without the presence of miR-21 was in the size range of 0.3-1250 nm with a PDI of 0.5 and the size range of the DNA nanomachine in the presence of miR-21 was in the size range of 0.3-10 nm with a PDI of 0.1. Also, the AFM microscope image of the DNA nanomachine without the presence of miR-21 and in the presence of miR-21 also clearly showed the reduction in the size of the nanoparticles with the intervention of miR-21. Also, the electrophoresis image on a 2% gel of DNA nanomachine without the presence of miR-21 and DNA nanomachine in the presence of miR-21 revealed that the addition of miR-21 caused the destruction of large nanostructures and the removal of the corresponding band. Examining the melting curve of DNA nanomachine without the presence of miR-21 and in the presence of miR-21 also determined that the presence of miR-21 causes the removal of secondary structures.

Keywords: DNA nanomachine, Advanced technologies, Cellular and molecular facts.

Received: 7 May 2025
Revised: 30 June 2025
Accepted: 15 October 2025
Published: 17 October 2025

Citation:

Shariat, S.; 1, Mowla, S.J.; Jebali, A. DNA nanomachine to target miR-21 and determine its structural and functional characteristics. *Special issue: Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **2025**, *1-16*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms26146754-1>

Copyright: ©2025 by the authors. Licensee MDPI, Basel, Switzerland. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

DNA nanomachines are inspired by biological molecular machines that can be observed in living systems. Several nanomachines have been developed to realize rotational, reciprocating, and walking motions. DNA molecular machines mainly operate by removing and adding specific DNA strands to induce DNA strand hybridization. In addition to hydrogen bonding, stacking forces play an important role in double-stranded DNA hybridization (1-5). In particular, DNA strands with an additional DNA, toehold, are used to perform diverse and complex movements. The addition of a complementary strand containing a toehold moiety allows for the induction of DNA strand exchange from pre-assembled dsDNA (strand displacement reaction). Thus, DNA strands can be replaced in the direction of thermodynamic stability by using energy differences to hybridize DNA strands. Using this method DNA scissors that can reversibly change and open their closed structure are created by controlling the binding and separation of two DNA strands (the regulated strand and the unregulated strand) (DNA molecular systems, such as walkers DNA which is completely controlled by multi-stranded displacements and DNA motors that move forward independently via an enzyme) has been engineered to achieve directional motion. Since hybridization/dehybridization of DNA strands containing toeholds is used to operate nanomachines, the speed of operation is influenced by the length and sequence (C/G and A/T content) and depends on the kinetics of hybridization and dehybridization of the DNA strands of DNA nanomachines, a controllable molecular system is required in which the nanomachines are programmed to operate by specific DNA strands. Seeman and his colleagues conducted pioneering studies on combining molecular machines with DNA nanostructures. Using a structural change of dsDNA called the BZ transition, in which the dsDNA structure changes from a right-handed structure (B-form DNA) to a left-handed structure (Z-form DNA) (Z-form changes, a reciprocating motion of the DNA nanostructure was observed. Furthermore, those authors developed molecular machines capable of 180° rotation at the ends of two adjacent dsDNA, called the PX-JX2 device, by hybridization and removal (5-10). They also obtained triangular DNA nanostructures by introducing two devices onto the DNA origami and rotating each triangle. Using this method, four types of PX-JX2 patterns can be operationalized by specific DNA strands, and four different types of nanostructures can be obtained. To simplify the design of complex strand displacement systems with fewer molecular components and to achieve flexible control over strand displacement kinetics, it is valuable to add novel toehold tuning mechanisms to the current strand displacement toolbox. miR-21, also known as hsa-mir-21. Or Also known as miRNA21, it is a mammalian microRNA encoded by the MIR21 gene. miR-21. It is one of the miRNAs frequently upregulated in solid tumors, and its elevated levels were first described in B-cell lymphomas. In general, miR-21. It is considered a typical “onco-miR” that acts by inhibiting interleukin 21 phosphatases. It is a biomarker for various cancers and demonstrated its potential as a tool for early diagnosis, associated with survival in breast cancer patients. miR-21 can also be detected in human. DNA toehold is used to guide the design and operation of a DNA device. This function is usually performed by separating a toehold in one DNA duplex between Or, an intramolecular synaptic cleft can be achieved that can then be activated. To construct devices with higher complexity, cascades of toehold exchange reactions can be programmed to detect complex environmental signals involving multiple input sequences. This MicroRNAs act like nanomachines and can recognize different sequences. MicroRNA 21, also known as hsa-mir-21. Or miRNA21 is also known, a mammalian microRNA, and is frequently expressed in solid tumors, and its high levels were first described in B-cell lymphomas.

In this study, we aim to design and synthesize a novel DNA nanomachine without the use of nanoparticles, with a large number of sequences, and at a much lower cost, and we hypothesize that it will be useful for measuring miR-21 in blood, intra and extracellular fluids, and cancer cells in the future. (10-15).

Materials and methods

Design and synthesis of DNA nanomachine

In this study, single-stranded oligonucleotides were first designed to target miR-21, which was adapted from the design of Wang et al.'s paper in 2016. In this study, 7 single-stranded DNA oligonucleotides complementary to the miR-21 sequence were synthesized (21). The ordered single-stranded oligonucleotide sequence from the 5' to 3' end was as follows:

TGTCGGGTAGCTTATCAGACTGAT, AAAGACA, ACCCTTT, AAAAGCT, GATATTT, AAAGTCT, ATCATTT

After synthesizing the designed oligonucleotides, first a concentration of 20 nM of them was prepared and after dilution, all were adjusted to 1 nM. Then 10 μ L of each was taken separately and poured into a microtube and then heated at 95°C for 5 minutes. The reaction mixture was then allowed to reach ambient temperature in a gradient manner over 15 minutes. This solution was used for structural and functional characterization. **Figure 1** shows a schematic of the designed nanomachine.

Figure 1. The schematic of the designed nanomachine. The ordered single-stranded oligonucleotide sequence from the 5' to the 3' end was as follows: TGTCGGGTAGCTTATCAGACTGAT, AAAGACA, ACCCTTT, AAAAGCT, GATATTT, AAAGTCT, ATCATTT.

The miR-21 intervention

In this step, the designed and synthesized oligonucleotides were placed in the presence of the miR-21 sequence and the annealing process was carried out exactly as in the above step, and the nanomachine was characterized. Here, too, 10 μ l of each oligonucleotide with a concentration of 1 nanomolar was taken separately and poured into a microtube, and 10 μ l of miR-21 with a concentration of 1 nanomolar was added and the same as above was placed at 95 for 5 minutes, and then the reaction mixture was allowed to reach room temperature for 15 minutes.

Characterization of DNA nanomachine and the effect of miR-21 intervention with electrophoresis test

The electrophoresis method with 2% agarose was also used. The reason for the electrophoresis test is to place the DNA nanomachine on the gel and confirm its formation and to determine its size compared to the ladder.

To perform the electrophoresis test, 2 microliters of the synthesized nanomachine were mixed with 2 microliters of DNA dye (FloraDye) and placed in a 2% agarose well, and separation was performed after one hour at a voltage of 50 V in TAE buffer. Then, the respective gel was placed in a gel dock and the gel was imaged.

Characterization of DNA nanomachines and the effect of miR-21 interference with Realtime PCR test

A melting curve test was also performed with a Real Time PCR device in the presence of Cyber Green dye. The reason for the melting curve test is that it is important for us to know what secondary structures are formed from the DNA of the machine. To do this, the DNA of the machine was synthesized and the Cyber Green dye was placed in temperature conditions from left to right: 95 °C, 65 °C, 37 °C, 25 °C, and its melting curve was photographed. In this test, 2 microliters of each synthesized oligonucleotide were poured into a special microtube of the real-time device with the same molar ratio, and 2 microliters of double-distilled water were added, then 18 microliters of Cyber Green Master Mix were added to it. Then, the same process was repeated exactly, but instead of 2 microliters of distilled water, 2 microliters of microRNA were added. Then, both microtubes were inserted into the Real Time PCR device and the following temperature-time program was run:

5 minutes, 95°C, 1 cycle- 5 minutes, 65°C, 10 cycles- 5 minutes, 37°C, 10 cycles-5 minutes, 25°C, 1 cycle. Then, the melting curve was taken from both microtubes and its image was saved.

Characterization of the synthesized nanomachine using AFM and DLS techniques

The AFM technique was used to determine the shape of the designed nanomachine. For this, 50 microliters of the synthesized vial in the presence and absence of miR-21 were poured onto a slide and after drying, it was given to Mahamax Company to be evaluated using an AFM microscope. Also, the DLS technique was used to determine the size range of the designed nanomachine and the secondary structures created. For this purpose, a diluted solution (1:10) of the synthesized vial in the presence and absence of miR-21 was given to the DLS device and the size range of the nanoparticles was determined.

Results

DLS

Figure 2a shows the size range graph of DNA nanomachines without the presence of miR-21 and **Figure 2b** shows the size range graph of DNA nanomachines in the presence of miR-21. The reduction in the size of nanoparticles with the intervention of miR-21 can be clearly seen. Because the size range of DNA nanomachines without the presence of miR-21 was in the size range of 0.3-1250nm and with an average size of 307.1 nm with a PDI of 0.5 and the size range of DNA nanomachines in the presence of miR-21 was in the size range of 0.3-10nm with a PDI of 0.1. Of course, there were also very large values.

Figure 2. The Size range graph of DNA nanomachines without the presence of miR-21 (a) and in the presence of miR-21 (b). The size range of DNA nanomachines without the presence of miR-21 was in the size range of 0.3-1250nm with an average of 307.1 nm with a PDI of 0.5. The size range of DNA nanomachines in the presence of miR-21 was in the size range of 0.3-10nm with an average of 1 nm with a PDI of 0.1.

AFM

Figures 3-7 show AFM microscope images of DNA nanomachines with and without miR-21. AFM microscope images of DNA nanomachines in the presence of miR-21. Here, too, the reduction in nanoparticle size with the intervention of miR-21 can be seen (**Figure 8**).

Electrophoresis

Figure 9 shows the electrophoresis image of the gel containing the DNA nanomachine without the presence of miR-21 and the electrophoresis image of the DNA nanomachine in the presence of miR-21, as well as the ladder bands. Here, it was also found that the addition of miR-21 caused the destruction of large nanostructures and the removal of the corresponding band.

Real Time PCR Results

Figure 10 shows the melting curve of the DNA nanomachine without the presence of miR-21 (a) and in the presence of miR-21 (b). Here, it was also found that the presence of miR-21 caused the removal of secondary structures. In both samples, a sharp peak is observed at 75°C.

Figure 3. AFM microscope image of DNA nanomachines without miR-21

Figure 4. AFM microscope image of DNA nanomachines without miR-21. Here, the reduction in nanoparticle size with the intervention of miR-21 can be seen.

Figure 5. AFM microscope image of DNA nanomachines without miR-21

Figure 6. AFM microscope image of DNA nanomachines in the presence of miR-21.

Figure 7. AFM microscope image of DNA nanomachines in the presence of miR-21. Here we can see the reduction in nanoparticle size with the intervention of miR-21

Figure 8. Histogram results of AFM images of DNA nanomachines without (a) and in the presence of miR-21. (b). Here we can also see the reduction in nanoparticle size with the intervention of miR-21

Figure 9. Electrophoresis gel image of the kb1 ladder (L1), the DNA nanomachine without the presence of miR-21 (L2) and the DNA nanomachine in the presence of miR-21 (L3). Here, it was also found that the addition of miR-21 caused the destruction of large nanostructures and the removal of the corresponding band.

Figure 10. Melting curve of DNA nanomachine without miR-21 (a) and in the presence of miR-21 (b). The presence of miR-21 caused the removal of secondary structures. In both samples, a sharp peak is observed at 75°C.

Discussion

Over the past decades DNA dynamic nanotechnology, which is regulated by DNA assembly-based actuator-responsive systems, has emerged over time, enabling precise and predictable dynamic manipulation of DNA structures. The key to constructing DNA assembly-based actuator systems is the integration of DNA assemblies and stimuli-responsive units together. Stimulus-responsive units can be integrated with DNA assemblies by covalent and noncovalent methods. Once this integration is established, the rapid, reversible, and remotely controllable properties of the stimuli-responsive unit can be transferred to the DNA assembly, providing a rich “toolbox” for the regulation of DNA nanostructures and functions (15-18).

Along with the rapid development of DNA nanotechnology and the increasing enrichment of stimuli-responsive units, DNA assembly-based responsive systems have emerged in 1D, 2D and 3D DNA nanostructures, including DNA architectures, DNA hybrid architectures, which greatly enrich the DNA nanostructure library and provide abundant materials for DNA-based bioimaging, biotherapy, etc. DNA assembly-based responsive stimuli-responsive systems have also been used to fabricate DNA nanomachines

and structural dynamic networks that mimic mechanical functions and dynamic interactions in nature, respectively. In addition, a series of biosensors targeting metal ions, nucleic acids, proteins, small molecules, pH values, temperature, etc. have been developed based on DNA assembly-based responsive stimuli-responsive systems, which are an important basis for their application in biomedicine. Multi-stimulus responsive systems based on DNA assembly, which can perform many functions simultaneously, have been on the rise. They have shown extraordinary performance in biological imaging (fluorescence imaging, MRI imaging) and therapy (chemotherapy, photothermal therapy (PTT), photodynamic therapy (PDT), and gene therapy) have been shown (18-22).

DNA assembly-based nanomachines that perform experiments on physical quantities or follow biological behavior have emerged as valuable biophysical tools for investigating physical and biological mechanisms at the nanoscale or single-molecule level. DNA assembly-based stimulus-responsive systems and dynamic networks have recently attracted considerable research efforts. Such dynamic control has great potential for applications in the fields of DNA computing, DNA information storage, and biological interaction networks. While DNA assembly-based responsive actuator systems have opened new frontiers in dynamic DNA nanotechnology, challenges and potential remain. Progress in any of the following challenges will give DNA assembly-based responsive actuator systems better applications: (22-25).

Stimulus-responsive units can sense external physical or chemical stimuli and change states (including composition, properties, behavior, etc.) in prescribed ways. However, there is still much room for the expansion of stimulus-responsive units. For example, most stimulus-responsive units only transition between two specific states after sensing stimuli. The types of stimulus-responsive units based on similar mechanisms are still very limited. Therefore, we expect to make progress in the mechanisms or numbers of stimulus-responsive units. A database may be developed to screen simple and effective stimulus-responsive units to meet functional needs. For example, the response accuracy and range of the triplex structure to pH values can be tuned. Therefore, it is possible to construct complex stimulus-responsive units for multi-state transition. Furthermore, the development of novel optical sensors or light-sensitive nanomaterials, temperature-responsive polymers, and electrically responsive redox reactions can expand the stimuli-responsive units. They have been reduced with the help of a suite of computer software such as NUPACK, CaDNAno, and CanDo, and DNA nanotechnology has made it possible to approach the complexity of natural structures, machines, and devices. The challenge here is to strike a better balance between design simplicity, functional complexity, high costs, and research technique. For example, optimal design with performance in mind can be achieved through more sophisticated software. Advances in DNA synthesis can reduce the cost of DNA molecules. Advanced techniques, such as cryo-electron microscopy (cryo-EM), molecular dynamics (MD), and small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS), can accurately reveal additional features of dynamic DNA nanostructures. This requires collaborative efforts in many fields, including chemistry, biology, physics, computer science, engineering, etc. (26-30). DNA complexes and stimuli-responsive units is the key and foundation of responsive systems based on DNA assembly. At present, the integration of DNA-responsive and non-DNA stimulus units usually requires complex processes that are not cost-effective in terms of time and cost. Recently, it has been reported that non-DNA molecular systems can dynamically control DNA by directly mixing with the DNA system according to the electrical, dynamic, and thermodynamic properties of DNA itself. It is believed that with the expansion of research on the characteristics of DNA and stimuli-responsive units,

molecular stimuli-responsive systems can be developed to understand the macrodynamic regulation of DNA systems and provide more space for the selection of DNA sequences. The composition or function of negatively charged DNA can be tuned by metal cations or positively charged polymers, and the assembly and disassembly of DNA nanostructures can be regulated by the protonation and deprotonation of pH-responsive organic molecules. . DNA assembly-based responsive actuator systems , it is necessary to consider their different requirements for specific functions. Sensitivity, accuracy, timeliness, reversibility, versatility, and synergy are all very important considerations. For example, precision is one of the most important factors to ensure the assembly of nanostructures, which is as important as sensitivity and timeliness. The assembly time of a complex 3D nanostructure usually takes several days. The most important function of DNA nanomachines is sensitivity and reversibility to achieve their physical or biological functions. In addition, for biomedical applications, sensitivity, versatility, and timeliness are crucial for bioassays, and synergy can provide valuable information for combination therapy. Therefore, rational design and combination of stimuli-responsive units with different response functions will have a profound impact on promoting the application of DNA assembly-based responsive actuator systems (30-35).

DNA nanotechnology offers unique opportunities for *in vivo* bioimaging and biotherapy due to the precise programmability and dynamic responsiveness of DNA -based dynamic nanostructures. The *in vivo* application of dynamic DNA nanotechnology requires careful consideration of many factors. On the one hand, the adverse effects of dynamic DNA nanostructures on living systems must be overcome, such as the biological toxicity of external stimuli, to ensure that no serious irreversible damage to the living body will be caused in the process. On the other hand, the impact of living organisms on dynamic DNA nanostructures must be considered. For example ,DNA nanostructures must enter the cell through the natural barrier of the cell membrane, escape degradation in the lysosome, and remain stable in the cycling process to achieve the ideal therapeutic effect. The prospect of using dynamic DNA nanotechnology in clinical therapy is still in its infancy, but the potential applications of responsive stimulus systems based on DNA assembly should not be underestimated for the following reasons: Direct external stimuli such as light, heat, and electricity can be remotely controlled, and thus DNA assembly-based stimulus-responsive systems have great potential in light, heat, and electrodynamic therapy. Organisms have temperature ,pH ,and ion-regulating systems, and DNA shows superior biocompatibility, therefore, corresponding DNA assembly-based responsive systems can be applied *in vivo* .DNA assembly-based stimulus-responsive systems can be coordinated with complex biological systems to realize multi-channel regulation of biological systems. (30-32). Chen showed that toehold-mediated strand displacement is very powerful in programming enzyme-free DNA circuits and DNA nanomachines . To achieve multistep, autonomous, and complex behaviors ,toeholds must first be inactivated by hybridization to inhibitory strands or domains and then released from inactivation in a programmed and timed manner. This study was also in line with our study . Anthony J. Genot et al. proposed that hybridization of DNA strands can be used to fabricate molecular devices and that controlling the kinetics of DNA hybridization is a critical element in the design and fabrication of functional, autonomous devices. Toehold-mediated strand displacement has proven to be a powerful mechanism that allows for programmable control of DNA hybridization. So far, efforts to control the kinetics of hybridization have mainly focused on the length and binding strength of toehold sequences. Inserting a spacer between the toeholds and the displacement domains provides further control: modulation of the nature and length of the spacer can be used to control the rate of strand displacement over at least 3 orders of magnitude

Zhang, D. Y. et al. explained that the specificity and predictability of Watson–Crick base pairing make DNA a powerful and versatile material for nanoscale engineering. This has enabled the fabrication of a diverse and rapidly growing array of DNA nanostructures and nanodevices through the programmed hybridization of complementary strands. Although initially focused on the self-assembly of static structures, DNA nanotechnology has now become increasingly attractive for engineering systems with interesting dynamic properties. Various devices, including circuits, catalytic replicators, autonomous molecular motors, and reconfigurable nanostructures, have recently been rationally designed to utilize DNA strand displacement reactions, in which two strands with partial or complete complementarity hybridize, displacing one or more prehybridized strands in the process. This mechanism allows for kinetic control of reaction pathways. Yurke et al. proposed that molecular recognition between complementary DNA strands could enable nanometer-scale fabrication. For example, DNA tags may be used to organize the assembly of colloidal particles, and DNA templates can guide the growth of semiconductor nanocrystals and metal wires. As a structural material, DNA can be used to fabricate static arrays of tiles, interconnected loops, and polyhedra. It is also possible to construct active devices—for example, a nanomechanical switch, whose structure changes by causing a transition in the chirality of the DNA double helix. Melting of chemically modified DNA has been induced by light absorption, and structural changes induced by the attachment of oligonucleotides or other small groups have been shown to alter the enzymatic activity of ribozymes. Here we report the construction of a DNA machine in which DNA is used not only as a structural material but also as a “fuel.” The device, made of three strands of DNA, is shaped like a pair of tweezers. It may be closed and opened by adding auxiliary DNA “fuel.” Each cycle produces a duplex DNA waste product. Georg Seelig and colleagues explained that biological organisms perform complex tasks of information processing and control using complex biochemical circuits, yet the engineering of such circuits remains elusive compared to electronic circuits. To systematically create complex yet reliable circuits, electrical engineers use digital logic, in which gates and subcircuits are built modularly, and signal recovery prevents signal degradation. We report the design and experimental implementation of DNA-based digital logic circuits. We demonstrate AND, OR, and NOT gates, signal recovery, amplification, feedback, and cascading. The gate design and circuit construction are modular. The gates use single-stranded nucleic acids as inputs and outputs, and the mechanism relies exclusively on sequence recognition and strand displacement. Biological nucleic acids such as microRNAs can serve as inputs, suggesting applications in biotechnology and bioengineering. David Yu Zhang and colleagues reported that synthetic biochemical circuits are likely to play a role in biological engineering as important as electrical circuits have played in the engineering of electromechanical devices. In this regard, nucleic acids provide a designable platform for regulating biochemical reactions. However, the synthesis of signal-amplifying components has been difficult. We introduce a design strategy that allows a specific input oligonucleotide to catalyze the release of a specific output oligonucleotide, which in turn can act as a catalyst for other reactions. This reaction, driven by the configurational entropy of the released molecule, provides an amplifier circuit element that is simple, rapid, modular, combinable, and robust. We have constructed and characterized several circuits that amplify nucleic acid signals, including a feedforward cascade with quadratic kinetics and a positive feedback loop with exponential growth kinetics. Yang and Hekaran reported a DNA nanomachine constructed from a DNA-functionalized gold nanoparticle (DNA-AuNP), which moves a DNA walker along a three-dimensional 3D DNA-AuNP track and performs the task of releasing cargo. The DNA walker motion is powered by a nicking endonuclease that cleaves specific DNA substrates along the track. During the motion, each DNA walker cleaves multiple substrates,

leading to the rapid release of cargoes (pre-designed DNA sequences and their combinations). The 3D DNA nanomachine is highly efficient due to the high local effective concentrations of all DNA components conjugated simultaneously on the same AuNP. Furthermore, the activity of the 3D DNA nanomachine can be controlled by introducing a protective DNA probe that can hybridize to or dissociate from the target in a specific manner. This feature allows us to tune the DNA nanomachine into a DNA nanosensor capable of rapid, isothermal, and homogeneous signal amplification for specific nucleic acids in buffer and a complex biometric DNA walkers capable of traversing three-dimensional paths have attracted much attention, as reported by Wang et al. However, DNA walker-based biosensors exhibit limited amplification efficiency due to slow walking kinetics. Here, taking advantage of the high throughput of the DNA walker device, a sensitive DNA nanomachine biosensor is designed. This biosensor is equipped with hairpin-loaded AuNPs (hpDNA@AuNPs). AgNCs as DNA walker and magnetic nanoparticles (AgNCs@MNPs) were fabricated as DNA walker devices. In the presence of target DNA, the DNA walker hybridized to exonuclease III (Exo III) is activated to carry out the first-step reaction via a displacement mechanism, and large amounts of toehold-loaded AuNPs (Toehold@AuNPs) are used to hybridize with AgNCs@MNPs with the help of Exo III. These cause rapid rotation of AuNPs on the surface of AgNCs@MNPs, releasing free AgNCs and converting the biological signal into the mass spectrometric signal ratio ($^{107}\text{Ag}/^{197}\text{Au}$) by ICP-MS detection. A linear range of 0.5–500 fmol L⁻¹ with a detection limit of amol L⁻¹ for the p53 gene is obtained. The practical application of the biosensor in the accurate measurement of the p53 gene in human blood has been demonstrated (30-35).

Conclusion

In this study, we aimed to design and center a DNA nanomachine with a new design without using nanoparticles and a large number of sequences, as well as at a much lower cost, and our assumption was that it would be useful for measuring miR-21 in blood, intracellular and extracellular fluids, and cancer cells in the future. The DLS test in this study showed a decrease in the size of the DNA nanomachine nanoparticles with the intervention of miR-21. The size range of the DNA nanomachine without the presence of miR-21 was in the size range of 0.3-1250nm with a PDI of 0.5, and the size range of the DNA nanomachine in the presence of miR-21 was in the size range of 0.3-10nm with a PDI of 0.1. Also, the AFM microscope image of the DNA nanomachine without the presence of miR-21 and in the presence of miR-21 also showed a decrease in the size of the nanoparticles with the intervention of miR-21. Also, the 2% gel electrophoresis image of DNA nanomachine without miR-21 and DNA nanomachine in the presence of miR-21 revealed that the addition of miR-21 caused the destruction of large nanostructures and the removal of the corresponding band. Melting curve analysis of DNA nanomachine without miR-21 and in the presence of miR-21 also revealed that the presence of miR-21 caused the removal of secondary structures. It is suggested that a three-dimensional DNA nanosensor for DNA detection using the A-toehold strand be developed in an independent study. It is suggested that other microRNAs be evaluated by the same method. It is suggested that nanomachines with other designs be developed and compared. Overall, DNA assembly-based stimulus-responsive systems have shown great potential in the fields of nanofabrication, biomedical applications, biocomputing, information storage, etc. Dynamic DNA systems with high controllability would be suitable for breaking the bottlenecks of DNA nanotechnology.

Reference:

1. Bath J, Turberfield AJ. DNA nanomachines. *Nature nanotechnology*. 2007;2(5):275-84.
2. Yurke B, Turberfield AJ, Mills Jr AP, Simmel FC, Neumann JL. A DNA-fuelled molecular machine made of DNA. *Nature*. 2000;406(6796):605-8.
3. Zhang DY, Seelig G. Dynamic DNA nanotechnology using strand-displacement reactions. *Nature chemistry*. 2011;3(2):103-13.
4. Mao C, Sun W, Shen Z, Seeman NC. A nanomechanical device based on the B–Z transition of DNA. *Nature*. 1999;397(6715):144-6.
5. Yan H, Zhang X, Shen Z, Seeman NC. A robust DNA mechanical device controlled by hybridization topology. *Nature*. 2002;415(6867):62-5.
6. Gu H, Chao J, Xiao S-J, Seeman NC. Dynamic patterning programmed by DNA tiles captured on a DNA origami substrate. *Nature nanotechnology*. 2009;4(4):245-8.
7. Gu H, Chao J, Xiao S-J, Seeman NC. A proximity-based programmable DNA nanoscale assembly line. *Nature*. 2010;465(7295):202-5.
8. Lund K, Manzo AJ, Dabby N, Michelotti N, Johnson-Buck A, Nangreave J, et al. Molecular robots guided by prescriptive landscapes. *Nature*. 2010;465(7295):206-10.
9. Wang F, Liu X, Willner I. DNA switches: from principles to applications. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*. 2015;54(4):1098-129.
10. Asanuma H, Liang X, Nishioka H, Matsunaga D, Liu M, Komiyama M. Synthesis of azobenzene-tethered DNA for reversible photo-regulation of DNA functions: hybridization and transcription. *Nature protocols*. 2007;2(1):203-12.
11. Liang X, Mochizuki T, Asanuma H. A supra-photoswitch involving sandwiched DNA base pairs and azobenzenes for light-driven nanostructures and nanodevices. *Small*. 2009;5(15):1761-8.
12. Wang F, Lu C-H, Willner I. From cascaded catalytic nucleic acids to enzyme–DNA nanostructures: controlling reactivity, sensing, logic operations, and assembly of complex structures. *Chemical reviews*. 2014;114(5):2881-941.
13. Yong J, Chen F, Yang Q, Du G, Shan C, Bian H, et al. Bioinspired transparent underwater superoleophobic and anti-oil surfaces. *Journal of Materials Chemistry A*. 2015;3(18):9379-84.
14. Heuer-Jungemann A, Kirkwood R, El-Sagheer AH, Brown T, Kanaras AG. Copper-free click chemistry as an emerging tool for the programmed ligation of DNA-functionalised gold nanoparticles. *Nanoscale*. 2013;5(16):7209-12.
15. Zhou Z, Liu X, Yue L, Willner I. Controlling the catalytic and optical properties of aggregated nanoparticles or semiconductor quantum dots using DNA-based constitutional dynamic networks. *ACS nano*. 2018;12(11):10725-35.

16. Wang C, Yue L, Willner I. Controlling biocatalytic cascades with enzyme–DNA dynamic networks. *Nature Catalysis*. 2020;3(11):941-50.
17. Lu S, Shen J, Fan C, Li Q, Yang X. DNA Assembly-Based Stimuli-Responsive Systems. *Adv Sci (Weinh)*. 2021;8(13):2100328.
18. Marsh RE, Bierstedt R, Eichhorn EL. The crystal structure of cytosine-5-acetic acid. *Acta Crystallographica*. 1962;15(4):310-6.
19. Hartman Jr KA, Rich A. The tautomeric form of helical polyribocytidylic acid. *Journal of the American Chemical Society*. 1965;87(9):2033-9.
20. Akinrimisi EO, Sander C, Ts'o P. Properties of helical polycytidylic acid. *Biochemistry*. 1963;2(2):340-4.
21. Inman RB. Transitions of DNA homopolymers. *Journal of molecular biology*. 1964;9(3):624-37.
22. Gehring K, Leroy J-L, Guéron M. A tetrameric DNA structure with protonated cytosine-cytosine base pairs. *Nature*. 1993;363(6429):561-5.
23. Mergny J-L. Fluorescence energy transfer as a probe for tetraplex formation: the i-motif. *Biochemistry*. 1999;38(5):1573-81.
24. Guéron M, Leroy J-L. The i-motif in nucleic acids. *Current opinion in structural biology*. 2000;10(3):326-31.
25. Kang C, Berger I, Lockshin C, Ratliff R, Moyzis R, Rich A. Crystal structure of intercalated four-stranded d(C3T) at 1.4 Å resolution. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. 1994;91(24):11636-40.
26. Leroy J-L, Gueron M, Mergny J-L, Helene C. Intramolecular folding of a fragment of the cytosine-rich strand of telomeric DNA into an i-motif. *Nucleic acids research*. 1994;22(9):1600-6.
27. Liu D, Balasubramanian S. A proton-fuelled DNA nanomachine. *Angewandte Chemie International Edition*. 2003;42(46):5734-6.
28. Dong Y, Yang Z, Liu D. DNA nanotechnology based on i-motif structures. *Accounts of chemical research*. 2014;47(6):1853-60.
29. Debnath M, Fatma K, Dash J. Chemical regulation of DNA i-motifs for nanobiotechnology and therapeutics. *Angewandte Chemie*. 2019;131(10):2968-83.
30. Hu Y, Ceconello A, Idili A, Ricci F, Willner I. Triplex DNA Nanostructures: From Basic Properties to Applications. *Angew Chem Int Ed Engl*. 2017;56(48):15210-33.
31. Li Y, Song L, Wang B, He J, Li Y, Deng Z, et al. Universal pH-Responsive and Metal-Ion-Free Self-Assembly of DNA Nanostructures. *Angew Chem Int Ed Engl*. 2018;57(23):6892-5.
32. Wang H, Chen Y, Wang H, Liu X, Zhou X, Wang F. DNAzyme-Loaded Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs) for Self-Sufficient Gene Therapy. *Angew Chem Int Ed Engl*. 2019;58(22):7380-4.

33. Duca M, Vekhoff P, Oussedik K, Halby L, Arimondo PB. The triple helix: 50 years later, the outcome. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2008;36(16):5123-38.
34. Radhakrishnan I, Patel DJ. DNA triplexes: solution structures, hydration sites, energetics, interactions, and function. *Biochemistry.* 1994;33(38):11405-16.
35. Wang Y, Zhao H, Zhou Q, Dai X, Liu K, Song D, et al. Monitoring the Structure-Dependent Reaction Pathways of Guanine Radical Cations in Triplex DNA: Deprotonation Versus Hydration. *J Phys Chem B.* 2019;123(13):2853-63.

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of MDPI and/or the editor(s). MDPI and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.